

Role of Human Resource Management and Quality Management in Higher Educational Institutions

Theme – “Innovative Functional Strategies for Gen Y “

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Abstract: *In any manufacturing organization there are large number of processes in which raw materials are converted into finished product with the help of resources like manpower, machines, materials, method, environmental characteristics for value addition. Various departments like Production, Purchase, Research and Development, Quality Management(QM), Maintenance, Human Resource Management (HRM) etc. which have interdependence on each other work together to produce **quality products** .Similarly in an educational institution there are different departments classified based on their expertise in delivering education in their respective domain which develop skills in students for the roles they need to perform in future and to increase their salability quotient .It is disheartening as well as surprising to know that most of the colleges in India do not have a Human Resource Management (HRM) Department and Quality Management (QM) Department. Some colleges have these departments but they are only for **namesake**. In order to explore their presence in colleges the survey is designed to find out who is performing the activities related to functions of QM and HRM in Jaipur based higher educational institutions and whether it is affecting the **work life balance** of faculty members and administrative staff. The survey also consists questions to check the **compliance to 12th Plan Guidelines for Establishment and Monitoring of the Internal Quality Assurance Cells in Colleges by the University Grants Commission** .The third objective is to find out how the presence of these departments is affecting the trainings organized for faculties and students and skill development .Some specific cases are also taken to show the effect of absence of QM and HRM and ineffective HRM and QM .It is done to highlight the importance of QM and HRM role*

in present scenario where customer centric culture is the need of the hour for working towards the fulfillment of the unaddressed needs of the direct and indirect customers of the institution i.e. parents, students (direct) recruiters and society (indirect).The research methods used are multi stage sampling , survey and case studies and sampling frame is Jaipur based Higher Educational Institutions .The study reveals that if organizations can remove the deficiencies in their HRM and QM then they will be on their way to become a World-Class institutions .In the concluding section the applicability and feasibility of all parameters related to Quality Management and Human Resource Management defined in ZED MATURITY ASSESSMENT MODEL for MSME’s is checked for Higher Educational Institutions .

Keywords: Salability Quotient, Work Life Balance, Internal Quality Assurance Cell, Customer Centric Culture, ZED Maturity Assessment Model

1.Introduction

Figure 1 District wise number of colleges [1]

According to [1]only affiliated and constituent institutions of Central and State Public Universities have been counted as colleges .**Constituent units of deemed /private universities , off campus centers and recognized centers have not been counted as colleges .**

HR Management and Quality Management Department perform some functions in each organization .

Figure 2 Human Resource Management Activities, Source [2]

The principles that govern the Quality Management Systems are written below.

Figure 2 Principles of Quality Management [3]

2. Research Methodology

Sampling Frame : Jaipur based Higher Educational Institutions

Data Source : Primary

Data Collection : 2 Surveys (consisting of open and closed ended questions) and case studies.

Sampling Method for first survey : Random Probability Sampling (Multi Stage Sampling) for first survey

Sampling Method for second survey : Non-Random Probability Sampling (Expert Sampling)

Figure 4.1 Sampling strategy and chosen samples for first survey

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First Survey :

The total number of higher educational institutions in Jaipur are 635 but 8 institutions participated in the survey .Hence the sample size is very low .The results can't be generalized to

all institutions but the shortcomings of the analyzed case studies and samples can be big learning's for all institutions .

2nd Survey :

The total number of respondents in second survey were 5 and all were Experts in ZED Maturity Assessment Model .

Limitation :One of the biggest limitation is the availability of NAAC reports of all the institutions .

3.Objectives

There were 3 objectives of the research .

1.To find out whether the absence of HR Department and Quality Department increases the burden on faculties .i.e apart from 16 hours of teaching workload how many hours faculties are devoting on Quality and HR Management related activities .

Figure 5 Presence of HR Department in chosen samples (Source : Survey 1)

At Parishkar College there is no HR Department so all the activities which are HR Department related are done by other departments .Also , the colleges where central HR is there like Apex College for Girls ,Jaipur Hospital College of Physiotherapy and Jaipur Hospital College of Nursing HR Department is not performing any activity at the college premises as per the feedback received by the survey respondents .At Sanskriti College HR is present but their role is

restricted to Performance review and Incentives .Hence 62% of participants in the survey from these 8 colleges felt that absence of HR is a burden for them .

Figure 7: Survey Results (Source :Survey1)

Figure 8 : Survey Results(Source : Survey 1)

Figure 9: Survey Results

There is no standard practice which is observed in all the colleges with respect to role performed by them and in some institutes owner is responsible for all HR activities .It appears that there is no job analysis done in these colleges .Also, new responsibilities are handed to people but there is no analysis available which shows number of spare hours available for handling the additional responsibility.

According to UGC Act the work load of a teacher shall take into account the following activities. **The details of the time devoted by faculties is not available except their teaching time (available in time table) .According to UGC Act no teacher shall be expected to lecture for more than three clock hours per day . [4]The teachers are devoting time in activities other than mentioned below which are specified by UGC as shown in figure 9,17,24 .Excess of workload certainly has an impact on work life balance of faculties and can be explored through further data collection and analysis .**

Figure 10 Workload distribution of faculties [4]

Figure 11 Permissible limits for number of students [4]

Figure 12: Survey Results (Source: Survey 1)

The above graph shows that even in colleges where HR department is present centrally and looking after the needs of more than one institute important activities like job analysis, employee satisfaction surveys are not done.

2.To find out the compliance to Internal Quality Assurance Guidelines laid down by UGC .

Functions of Internal Quality Assurance Cell

A diagram representing the functions of IQAC as mentioned in IQAC Guidelines laid down by UGC is shown below .

Figure 13: Functions of IQAC [5]

The colleges which are NAAC Accredited have to mandatorily develop an Internal Quality Assurance Cell .The compliance to organization structure should be according to below diagram.

Figure 15 Organization Structure of IQAC [5]

Figure 16 Survey Results (Source: Survey 1)

Hence the colleges like Apex College for Girls, Parishkar college should mandatorily have an AQAR report displayed on their website immediately and appoint people to be a part of their IQAC as per norms .Hence compliance of laws and guidelines is a question mark .

Activity	Apex College for Girls	Jaipur National University	Parishkar College	Amity University	BITS Jaipur	JHCN	JHCPT	Sanskriti College
Displaying the Annual Quality Assurance Cell report on the college website	Mgmt/Director/Principal+Administrative Department	TPO+HR+Faculty	Director/Principal/Management	Quality Department	Administrative Department	Director/Principal/Management	Admin Department	Not done
Preparing the Annual Quality Assurance Cell report and submitting to UGC	Not done	TPO + HR	Director/Principal/Management	Quality Department	Administrative Department	Director/Principal/Management+Registrar	Not done	Not done
Submission of Annual Quality Assurance Report to Accreditating bodies NAAC,NBA	Director/Principal/Management	TPO + HR	Director/Principal/Management	Quality Department	Administrative Department	Not Done	Admin Department	Not done
Submission of Annual Quality Assurance Report to State Quality Assurance Cell	Director/Principal/Management	TPO + HR	Director/Principal/Management	Quality Department	Administrative Department	Not Done	Not done	Not done
Organization of inter and intra institutional workshops , seminars on Quality related themes	Director/Principal/Management +Faculty	TPO + HR	Director/Principal/Management	Director/Principal/Management	Administrative Department	Director/Principal/Management+Registrar	Director/Principal/Management	Not done
Organization of inter and intra institutional workshops , seminars for promotion of Quality Circles	Director/Principal/Management +Faculty	TPO+HR+Faculty	Director/Principal/Management	Director/Principal/Management	Administrative Department	Director/Principal/Management+Registrar	Director/Principal/Management	Not done

Figure 17 Survey Results: Who performs which activity related to Quality?(Source : Survey 1)

The roles and responsibilities related to Internal Quality Assurance Cell are distributed to people performing different roles at different colleges but for each activity who is having the approving authority ,who will play the supportive role and who will be performing informing and coordinative tasks is not known .For eg : RASIC chart can be used for each activity .

R- Responsible

A- Approve

S- Support

I- Information

C- Coordination

Quality Function Deployment

Figure 18 Quality Function Deployment [6]

Figure 19 Survey Results (Source : Survey 1)

Though 62% of colleges confirmed that their Management Conducts Quality Function Deployment but **none of them displayed their QFD reports on the website** .QFD includes capturing the voice of the customer and finding out which parameters can help in accomplishing those requirements . For any higher educational institution primary customers are parents and students and secondary customers are recruiters ,society and government .QFD can be very useful in preparing AQAR but none of the colleges mentioned that .Probably their understanding of QFD is different from the conventional understanding .The following diagram shows the requirements and expectations of various stakeholders from an educational institute .

Figure 20 Stakeholder Expectation in Higher Educational Institutions [7] [8]

3. To find out whether Human Resource and Quality Mgmt. Department has an impact on skill development and trainings organized for faculties and students .

To find out the impact questions were asked which were related to academic performance indicator of faculties and how skills are measured and uniformity between recruiter's way of measuring skills and higher educational institution's way of measuring skills .The respondents did not give supportive evidence to support their answers .The number of training programs organized could not be found out as 6 colleges out of 8 did not display their **Annual Quality Assurance Report** on website. JNU AQAR revealed that the number of students passing out the examination is low.

The Survey results are shown below:

How they are measuring the skills of the students?

The various answers which were received are by-

1. Evaluating with different parameters
2. Specific skill trainings
3. Theory, practical internal and university exam and
4. Organizing competitions and other evaluation processes .It was an open question hence varied response is observed.
5. Online tests / Online Assessment Test / In house Psychometric Assessment tests
6. Participation in national/university/college level technical competitions.
7. Ability to perform the practical work in labs.
8. Ability to communicate and present topics in class.
9. Performances in various tests conducted by department.
- 10 .Ability to perform good in aptitude tests and programming test.

Is your way of measuring the skills of the students is the same as recruiter's way of measuring skills?

Figure 21 Survey Results (Source : Survey 1)

None of the participants discussed about the similarities and differences in recruiter’s method and Institutional method for measuring skills .None of the survey participants discussed about the following essentials of a selection test –

- 1.Reliability** – results can be repeated
- 2.Validity** – it should be able to confirm who is skilled and who is not
- 3.Objectivity** – should not be influenced by people’s opinion
- 4.Standardization** – should be performed under standard conditions .

Is faculty performance measured through Academic Performance Indicators introduced by UGC in your college?

Figure 22 Survey Results (Source : Survey 1)

Is there year on year updation of API scores of faculties?

Figure 23 Survey Results (Source : Survey 1)

None of the institutions mentioned that a Higher Annual Performance Indicator results in better skill development in students .**There are no studies done in these colleges in this respect that prove that faculty development and a greater API yields more skilled students .**

Students were not able to respond to the survey as they were not aware about who performs which role in an institution .

The activities which were related to both HR and Quality Management were listed and who performed which activity was asked .**Some activities were team efforts and some were individual and there was no uniformity observed in role performance as all colleges have their own procedures to perform an activity .Some of the HR and QM activities are not performed in any college.**

Who is responsible for the following activities in your college?

Figure 24 Survey Results (Source : Survey 1)

4. Hypothesis formulated and related results

Figure 25 Types of hypothesis testing

Table 1: Tests of association for various results obtained under survey 1 . [9]

Contingency table headings				Computed frequencies	Chi Square test of association application						
Yes ,Yes	Yes,No	No,Yes	No,No	Expected frequencies	Null Hypothesis	Alternative hypothesis	Chi Square Calculated	Chi Square Tabulated (alpha 0.05 level of significance), Degrees of freedom =(2-1)*(2-1)	Decision	Inference	Strength of Association (Φ) coefficient
4	3	1	0	4.375,2.625,0.625,0.375	There is no association between the organisations where HR is present and those who feel that absence of HR is a burden for administrative and teaching staff .	There is an association between the organisations where HR is present and those organisations where people feel that absence of HR is a burden for teaching and administrative staff .	0.6857	3.841	Null hypothesis accepted	There is no association between HR presence and the feelin that absence of HR is a burden on administrative staff and faculties.	
5	2	1	0	5.25,1.75,0.75,0.25	There is no association between presence of HR and IQAC creation	There is an association between presence of HR and IQAC creation	0.353051	3.841	Null hypothesis is accepted	There is no association between HR Presence and IQAC creation	
5	0	1	2	3.75,1.25,2.25,0.75	There is no association between Quality Function Deployment done and Faculty Performance measured through API .	There is an association between Quality Function Deployment done and Faculty performance measured through API .	4.4441	3.841	Null hypothesis is rejected	There is an association between Quality Function Deployment and Academic Performance Indicator .	0.7453
2	4	0	2	1.5,4.5,0.5,1.5	There is no association between Internal Quality Assurance Cell and Annual Quality Assurance Report .	There is an association between Internal Quality Assurance Cell and Annual Quality Assurance Report .	0.88891	3.841	Null hypothesis is accepted	There is no association between IQAC and AQAR but ideally there should be an association as preparation of AQAR is a part of compliance to IQAC guidelines	
2	4	0	2	1.5,4.5,0.5,1.5	There is no association between Internal Quality Assurance Cell and compliance to organisation structure.	There is an association between Internal Quality Assurance Cell and compliance to organisation structure.	0.88891	3.841	Null hypothesis is accepted	There is no association between IQAC and compliance to organisation structure but ideally there should be an association as compliance to organisational structure is a part of compliance to IQAC guidelines	
4	0	2	2	3,1,3,1	There is no association between NAAC Accreditation and IQAC creation .	There is an association between NAAC Accreditation and IQAC creation .	2.8333	3.841	Null hypothesis is accepted	There is no association between NAAC accreditation and IQAC creation	
5	2	1	0	5.25,1.75,0.75,0.25	There is no association between HR Presence and faculty performance measureent through API	There is an association between HR Presence and faculty performance measureent through API	0.3809	3.841	Null hypothesis is accepted	There is no association between HR Presence and faculty performance measurement through API	
6	0	0	2	4.5,1.5,1.5,0.5	There is no association between IQAC Presence and faculty performance measureent through API	There is an association between IQAC Presence and faculty performance measureent through API	8	3.841	Null hypothesis is rejected	There is an association between IQAC Presence and faculty performance measurement through API	

5.The Quality and HR related Questionnaire of ZED Maturity Assessment Model

ZED Maturity Assessment Model is in use for assessment of 10 disciplines in MSME’s which include Quality and HR Management discipline. The ZED Maturity Assessment Model consists of 50 parameters out of which 36 are **enablers** (denoted by A-N) and 14 are **outcome parameters** (denoted by O-R). [10]

A survey was prepared and the ZED Certified consultants who were trained in February 2018 by the Quality Council of India were asked questions related to the usage of same questionnaire for assessment of HR and Quality related parameters in higher educational institutions .5 people participated in the survey and following were the results -

Do you think that the questions on Quality Management in the ZED Certification scheme are applicable for higher educational institutions?

Figure 26.1 Survey Results (Source : Survey 2)

Do you think that the questions on Human Resource Management in the ZED Certification scheme are applicable for higher educational institutions?

Figure 26.2 Survey Results (Source : Survey 2)

The Enablers and Outcome Parameters of ZED Certification Scheme

Figure 27 Enabler and Outcome Parameters in ZED Certification Scheme [10]

Figure 28 Topics related to Quality Management in ZED Maturity Assessment Model [10]

In order to explain above parameters we can take the example of teaching process shown below and some flaws related to non-fulfillment of requirements related to man , machine ,method, material and environment which emerged during case studies

.Figure 29 Elements of teaching process

Figure 30 Steps to counter variation in teaching process [11]

Variation in teaching process can be because of skill level of students and teacher , cognitive ability of student and teacher, the difference in measurement methods, the different types of classrooms and the environment inside i.e. temperature , pressure ,humidity. The different types of classrooms are shown below .Hence all these parameters should be monitored regularly or standardized to ensure that there are no unacceptable results.

Figure 31 Steps to counter variation in teaching

Example of Ergonomically designed seating of lecture theatre. “Ergonomics is the process of designing or arranging workplaces, products and systems so that they fit the people who use them” [12] .At Indian Institute of Management Indore ergonomics are taken into account in the

designed lecture theatres where the chairs of students can rotate 360 degrees and hence the students do not face problem of **neck pain** .The height of the chairs can also be adjusted so that students can be comfortable when they are gaining knowledge.

One of the desired outcomes with all resources in place as per norms is that the student should attain good scores and can then apply for scholarships for attaining higher degree. One example of systemic flaw which is a hindrance in applying for scholarships or **Field Performance** (performance of students in their work areas where they apply attained knowledge at) sustenance is no release of merit of Engineering students of 2008 batch by Rajasthan University. Hence the then engineering pass-outs who may be the Merit Holders were and are still not able to apply for scholarships like **PG Scholarship for University Rank Holders (1st and 2nd Rank Holders)** . [13] **Earlier the criteria for PM Manmohan Singh Doctoral scholarship was also based on merit ranking but it was modified later on .** [14]

Figure 32 No release of merit by Rajasthan University is a hindrance for getting PG scholarship

Non-standardized content causes confusion: The Oxford Dictionary of different sizes available in the market is having different meaning given for same words which creates confusion in the mind of readers. The dictionaries are available in market but the publishers are different .Such variation in content is the reason for confusion in people and puts a question on content review and selection mechanism for publication.

S.No.	Word	Little Oxford Dictionary	Illustrated Oxford Dictionary	Oxford English-English Hindi Dictionary
1	regime	1.A government ,especially one that strictly controls a state 2.An ordered way of doing something ,a system	1. A government ,especially one that strictly controls a state 2.An ordered way of doing something ,a system	1.A method or system of government, especially one that has not been elected in a fair way 2. NOT FOUND

Figure 33 Mismatch of meanings found in Oxford Dictionaries available in market [15] [16] [17]

The ZED scheme questionnaire point L-1 People Development Plans under HR Management asks questions on how needs are identified for developing people .It also asks about competency mapping of people and their coaching and training plan and the adherence to development plan .Other questions are related to employee involvement where reward schemes are introduced for introducing improvements at workplace tracking of improvements is done .

Figure 34 Topics related to Human Resource Management in ZED Maturity Assessment Model

The relevant questions where a skill gap exists are- 1.Is the process capable for producing desired results? 2. Is the workforce competent enough to perform the required task?

Figure 35 Skill gap and it’s linkage to Quality and HR Department in HEI

Another example is that of syllabus up gradation and a new subject introduction but faculty knowledge not upgraded simultaneously to match the requirement .No competency mapping was available for faculties and no eligibility norms were not updated with respect to teaching Laws for Engineers.

Figure 36 Syllabus updation but faculty knowledge upgradation not done

The other case shown below is of Practical Lab at one of the Engineering Colleges of Jaipur where machine was not working but practical was conducted .There was no spare machine available and the lab was not outsourced .In turn the students compromised on the educational services rendered to them .The college did not map the gap generated because of this assignable cause as there was no awareness of Quality Management System in the students and their right to ask the college to ensure quality services .Also , the other cause was that there was no maintenance plan available at the college for the lab machines .The task was not deployed to faculty and lab incharges and the root cause for same was that the **HR Management department was not performing all it’s activities in a fully fledged way .Their role was restricted only to student placements and no job description and job analysis was done for the job of Mechanical Engineering faculties .**

Figure 36 Syllabus updation but faculty knowledge upgradation not done

Very difficult to bridge the gap in passed out engineers

Figure 48 Vibration lab not present but practical was conducted

Hence, these examples also demonstrate that the ZED Maturity Assessment Model can be a good tool to assess the **enablers and outcome parameters of Quality and Human Resource Department in higher educational institutions** .However in order to be eligible to answer some questions the institutions need to start ensuring that all activities related to HR and Quality Management are performed in their organization and they are aware about same .

5. Conclusion-

- There are no standardized job profiles in higher educational institutions as different people perform different roles in different institutes.
- The areas like employee satisfaction, job analysis, employee welfare are still untouched in educational sector samples .Same holds true for Quality Management areas like Field Performance ,regular feedback from parents etc .

- The tests of association revealed that there is no compliance of IQAC guidelines as there is no association between IQAC presence and organization structure and AQAR displayed on websites.
- The strong association of 0.745 (Φ phi coefficient) is found between **Quality Function Deployment and Academic Performance Indicator (API) and 1 (Φ phi coefficient) between IQAC and API.**
- A need for regular mechanism for assessment of the administrative and educational machinery of the college is there .
- ZED Maturity Assessment Model was proposed for assessing the Quality and HR Requirements of Higher Educational Institutions regularly and more than 80% of the ZED Certified Consultants agreed to this usage .
- Relevant case studies proved that the ZED Maturity Assessment Model can emerge as a regular monitoring mechanism for assessing the Quality and HR Requirements of HEI and the institutions need not wait for 5 years for NAAC to assess themselves .

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